

EFFECTS OF SPECIMEN WIDTH ON THE TENSILE STRENGTH OF ALIGNED SHORT-CARBON-FIBER REINFORCED EPOXY COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the size effects of specimen width on the tensile testing properties of aligned short carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite laminate. This is a kind of newly designed short fiber composite laminates and called unidirectionally arrayed chopped strands (UACS) laminates, fabricated by introducing discontinuous slits into the conventional continuous fiber prepreg. Tensile tests for specimens with different width cut from UACS laminates are conducted. Results of tests reveal that tensile strength increases with the increase of specimen width until the specimen width is equal to 25 mm. Failure modes are different for specimens with different width. Fiber breakage of 0° plies are observed only for specimens with width larger than 20 mm. The stress concentration at the free edge plays a main role for the effect of the specimen width on the tensile properties. Large delamination occurs near the free edge and around the cross points of the slits in the 0° and adjacent ±45° plies.

1 INTRODUCTION

The size effects are defined as a change in testing mechanical properties of a material with specimen dimensions, and this phenomenon is well-known to exist in composites [1-4]. Several studies have revealed the size effects in mechanical properties of composite laminates [5-11]. It is very complicated to clarify the size effects because of the different failure mechanisms, and the possibility of interaction among matrix cracking, delamination, and fiber failure. Jackson et al. [5-6] carried out tensile and bend tests of AS4/3502 carbon-epoxy specimens with cross-ply, angle-ply and quasi-isotropic lay-ups by changing all three dimensions together with ply level scaling. Of particular relevance are tests on [45_m/-45_m/0_m/90_m]_s laminates with *m* varying from 1 to 4. The tensile strength of specimens with *m* = 4 was reduced by 28% over that of specimens with *m* = 1. The failure strains apparently increased with the increase of *m*. There was also a change in failure mode from a localized fracture for the smaller specimens to more extensive fracturing throughout the specimen for the larger ones. Johnson et al. [7] carried out a series of tensile tests of sublaminates-level scaled laminates of AS4/3502 carbon fiber/epoxy. Various laminates including cross-ply laminates, angle-ply laminates, and quasi-isotropic laminates with the same [45/-45/0/90]_{ns} stacking sequence were tested. The number of sublaminates, *n*, was varied from 1 to 4, with specimen widths and lengths scaled in proportion. The results showed an

increase in tensile strength from the smallest specimens to the specimens with other sizes. This was attributed to the smallest specimens being more susceptible to free edge delamination. Wisnom et al. [8-11] carried out a series of research in size effects of composite laminates. Tensile tests were performed for $[45/-45/0/90]_n$ s fabricated by Hexcel IM7/8552 carbon fiber/epoxy, with n varying from 1 to 4 and with all the dimensions including gauge length, width, and thickness scaled in proportion. The testing results shown that the tensile strength increased with the increase of specimen size and that the largest specimens shown a strength 10% higher than that of smallest ones. There are many factors influencing size effects of composites, including material microstructure, stress gradients, and free edge effects. Among them, free edge effects derive from very high interlaminar stresses arising at the free edge of a laminate with different ply orientations. This phenomenon was studied in the work of Pipes and Pagano [12] onwards. In some laminates it leads to premature failure initiating at the free edge. The effects of free edges on in-plane failure are less well understood, but could be significant for many layups and types of loading. Berbinau and Wolff [13] argued that the interlaminar stresses at the free edge are important in initiating compressive failure in $[0/\pm \theta]$ laminates. According to above mentioned previous research in size effects of composite laminates. It is recognized that it is important to consider the size effects in scaling up from small coupon tests to full scale structures in design of composite structures.

In this paper, the size effects of specimen width on the tensile properties of aligned short carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite laminate is investigated. This aligned short fiber composite laminate is a kind of newly designed short fiber composite laminates and called unidirectionally arrayed chopped strands (UACS) laminates, fabricated by introducing discontinuous slits into the conventional continuous carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) prepreg. All the fibers are cut into short fibers with the same length [14-18]. The UACS laminates of has much higher carbon fiber volume fraction, stiffness, and strength than conventional short carbon fiber reinforced plastic composites. Tensile tests of specimens with five different widths (10 mm, 15 mm, 20 mm, 30 mm, 40 mm) cut from UACS laminates are conducted.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Fabrication of UACS laminates with three different slit-distribution patterns

Commercial available unidirectional CFRP prepreg of PYROFIL#350 (TR50S) (Mitsubishi Rayon) is used in this study. The material properties of this CFRP lamina are listed in Table 1. Fiber volume fraction (V_f) and thickness of the prepreg are 60% and 0.2 mm, respectively. Firstly, slits with regular distribution are introduced into the unidirectional and continuous CFRP prepreg by hand-cutting along the slit lines printed on a white paper adhered on the prepreg using a paper cutter. It is worth mentioning that the cutting process must be completed in a short time because the prepreg becomes soft gradually with the time at the room temperature and it is difficult to ensure the quality of uniform slits for too soft prepreg. Three kinds of UACS prepregs with three different slit distribution patterns, namely continuous angled slit pattern, staggered angled slit pattern, and bi-angle slit pattern, are made according to [15-18]. The continuous angled slit pattern was proposed in [15] and the other two patterns were proposed in [16, 17]. The schematics of three slit distribution patterns are depicted in Figure 1(a) and the related images of UACS prepregs, taken by a transparent photography technique, are presented in Figure 1(b). The slit angle between the slit and the fiber direction is 11.3 degrees in all cases of angled plies, and the length of chopped strands is 25 mm for all slit patterns. In other words, the fiber length of all UACS prepregs is 25 mm. The horizontal projection L_x of the slit length is 5 mm in all cases of UACS prepregs, as shown in Figure 1(a).

Quasi-isotropic UACS laminates used for tensile specimens are fabricated by the use of UACS prepregs with three different slit patterns. Firstly, the UACS prepregs of 0° , 45° , 90° and -45° are stacked in the sequence of $[45/0/-45/90]_s$. As a typical example, a schematic of stacking a laminate by UACS prepregs with bi-angled slits is depicted in Figure 2. All the stacked prepregs are cured using an autoclave. The cure cycle is recommended by the manufacturer of CFRP prepreg. The cure temperature and pressure are 127°C and 0.3 MPa, respectively. The thickness of all cured UACS quasi-isotropic laminates are about 1.6 mm. Microscopic observation of the polished edge surface of typical cured UACS laminates with three slit distribution patterns is performed using optical

microscope to investigate the microscopic structure of the UACS laminates and the images of slits in the each layer of the laminate.

PYROFIL#350 (TR50S) CFRP	
Longitudinal Young's modulus E_1 (GPa)	142
Transverse Young's modulus E_2 (GPa)	8.8
In-plane shear modulus G_{12} (GPa)	4.2
Out-of-plane shear modulus G_{23} (GPa)	3.7
In-plane Poisson's ratio ν_{12}	0.27
Out-of-plane Poisson's ratio ν_{23}	0.32
Longitudinal tensile strength X_t (MPa)	2950
Longitudinal compression strength X_c (MPa)	1570
Transverse tensile strength Y_t (MPa)	79
Transverse compression strength Y_c (MPa)	190
In-plane shear strength S_{12} (MPa)	140
Out-of-plane shear strength S_{23} (MPa)	88

Table 1 Material properties of PYROFIL#350 (TR50S) CFRP lamina

Figure 1: UACS prepreps with three different distribution patterns of slits.

2.2 Specimens and tensile tests

Tensile specimens of 200 mm in length are cut from the quasi-isotropic UACS laminates with three patterns slit distribution using a cutting machine with diamond cutter. The dimensions of

specimens with five widths including 10 mm, 15 mm, 20 mm, 30 mm, and 40 mm are described in Figure 3. Since the tensile testing for specimen with width 25 mm was conducted in [16], there are actually specimens with six different widths for the investigation of size effects of the specimen width on the tensile testing properties of the UACS laminates. Glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) tabs of 40 mm in length are adhered on two surfaces of the specimens. The gauge length of all the specimens is 120 mm and strain gauges of 10 mm in length are bonded at the centers of two surfaces of specimens. Tensile tests are conducted using Material-testing system MTS 810 and the crosshead speed is 0.5 mm/min. For each case of specimens with five widths and cut from three kinds of UACS laminates with three slit patterns, 4 tensile specimens are tested. Totally 60 tensile specimens are tested. The Effects of specimen width on the tensile stiffness, tensile strength, and failure behavior are investigated during the tensile testing and the optical observation of tested specimen.

Figure 2: Schematic of stacking a Quasi-isotropic UACS laminate with bi-angled slit pattern.

Figure 3: Dimensions of tensile specimens.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Typical image of slits in the polished edge of a cured UACS laminate with staggered slit distribution is presented in Figure 4. The horizontal length of this image is about 1.1 mm. Slits are observed in 0° , -45° , and 90° plies and no slit is seen in 45° ply within this photo. It is seen that slits are filled by epoxy resin and few fiber-debris are embedded in the resin-filled slits. It is considered that different dimensions of slits observed from different layers are mainly due to the different angle between the slit and the view direction. Slits in the other two UACS laminates with continuous angled slits and with bi-angled slits have the similar images. In addition, no obvious voids can be observed from the image.

Figure 4: Typical images of slits in a cured UACS laminate with staggered slit distribution.

Tensile testing results are described in following figures. Effects of specimen width on the testing tensile strength of specimens of three kinds of UACS laminates with different slit distribution patterns are depicted in Figure 5. It is worth mentioning that the data of the UACS laminates of 25 mm in width was obtained from previous tensile results of UACS laminate of $[45/-45/0/90]_{2S}$ [16]. From the testing data of Figure 5 it is seen that tensile strength increases with the increase of specimen width until the specimen width is equal to 25 mm. After then, the tensile strength tends to a stable level with the specimen width larger than 25 mm. The strength values of specimens of 40 mm in width increase about 18.3%, 26.2 % and 26.7% for three kinds of UACS laminates, respectively. These facts reveal that the specimen width has significant influence on the tensile testing strength. It is considered that the specimen width must be equal to or larger than 25 mm to obtain a reliable tensile strength of UACS laminates based on present tensile testing results. In addition, the specimens of UACS laminates with bi-angled slit distribution have the highest strength values while those of UACS laminates with the continuous slit distribution show the lowest values for all cases of specimen widths. These relationships among the tensile strength of three kinds of UACS laminates are consistent with the previous experimental results [16].

Figure 5: UACS preregs with three different distribution patterns of slits.

Typical strain-stress curves of specimens of UACS laminate with bi-angled slit distribution and are depicted for six different specimen widths in Figure 6. Nonlinear behavior near the peak values is observed in all the six curves and the nonlinear range becomes larger as the width of specimen becomes larger. The nonlinear behavior is considered to reflect the delamination occurring and propagation between 0° ply and its adjacent plies before the final breakage of 0° plies. Short nonlinear range means that the final failure happens immediately following the delamination occurring,

especially when the width of the specimen is less than 25 mm. In addition to the variation of tensile strength with the specimen width, the testing longitudinal modulus and final failure strain of the UACS laminates also increases with the increase of the specimen width. The detail data of longitudinal modulus and failure strain of specimens of UACS laminates with bi-angled slit distribution are described in Figure 7. Solid rectangle and white circle are testing data averaged over 4 specimens and solid lines are approximate curves. Rapidly increase in longitudinal modulus is observed from the specimens with 10 mm in width to 15 mm in width and then the modulus shows slight variation for specimens with width larger than 15 mm. In contrast, the final failure strain of the specimens from 10 mm in width to 25 mm in width shows a rapid increase and then it shows a slow increase. Similar effects of specimen width on the tensile testing properties are also observed from the specimens of other two kinds of UACS laminates. Therefore, the effects of specimen width on the tensile testing properties are significant and should be considered in the evaluation of the tensile properties of UACS laminates when the specimen width is less than 25 mm.

Figure 6: Typical stress-strain curves of specimens of UACS laminate with bi-angled slit distribution for six different specimen widths.

Figure 7: Effects of specimen width on the longitudinal modulus and final failure strain of specimens of UACS laminates with bi-angled slit distribution.

Typical images of fractured specimens of UACS laminates with bi-angled slits distribution and with three different specimen widths are shown in Figure 8. In the case of specimen with 10 mm in width, the failure mode of 0° plies is obviously a pull-out mode and no fiber breakage in 0° plies can be seen. Compared with the failure mode of 0° plies in the specimen with 10 mm in width, the images of the fractured specimens with 20 mm and 30 mm in width show a little different failure behavior. Many fibers in 0° plies are broken under tension and relatively few pull-out failure modes are seen. These facts indicate that the fibers in 0° plies still can sustain the load even though delamination occurred when the specimen have relative large width, these failure behavior may be related to the

nonlinear portion of the stress-strain curves. Large area of delamination and no fiber breakage result in relatively small nonlinear portion before final failure in the specimen with 10 mm in width. Similar effects of the specimen width on the tensile failure behavior of the UACS laminates with discontinuous staggered angled slits and with continuous angled slits are observed. For the simplicity, only the results of the UACS laminates with discontinuous bi-angled slits are discussed hereafter. In

Figure 8: Typical images of fractured specimens of UACS laminates with bi-angled slits distribution and with three different specimen widths.

Figure 9: Images of internal damage in the fractured specimen of 40 mm in width and with bi-angle slit distribution.

order to further investigate the damage progression in the UACS laminates, the cross-section 10 mm away from the fracture section of a specimen with the bi-angled slits and 40 mm in width is cut out and polished by sand paper. Then the polished surface is observed using an optical microscope. Three representative locations A, B and C along the width direction are observed in detail, as shown in the left-lower draft of Figure 9. Remarkable and penetrable delamination between 0° ply and adjacent -45° ply is observed near the free edge at location A. Location B presents the damage near the slit in 0° ply. Crack in slit of 0° ply is observed. Delamination between 0° ply and adjacent -45° and 45° plies occurs from the cross points of the crack in slit and the interfaces and then extends from the slit area to both opposite directions simultaneously. The left side of the delamination between the 0° ply and -45° ply connects with the delamination shown in the image at location A. However, the delamination does not extend a long distance along the width direction opposite to A. Similar feature is observed at the location C. From the observation at the three locations, it is considered that delamination easily initiates and extends near the free edge of the specimen and near the cross points of cracking slit of 0° ply and the interfaces between 0° ply and its two adjacent plies, but if the specimen has a relatively larger width it is not so easy for the delamination to grow into the specimen along the width direction since the stress concentration at the edge or at the slit tip is limited in a relatively small area. On the other hand, if the specimen width is too small the ratio of the stress concentration area and the specimen width becomes relatively large, the delamination occurred near the edge or near the slit easily extends through the width, which leads to the failure behavior of the specimen with 10 mm in width, as shown in Figure 8.

4 CONCLUSION

Size effects of the specimen width on the tensile testing properties of aligned short carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite laminates, namely, UACS laminate with three different slit distribution patterns, are investigated. Tensile tests of specimens with five different widths (10 mm, 15 mm, 20 mm, 30 mm, 40 mm) cut from UACS laminates are conducted. Size effects of the specimen width on the tensile strength, longitudinal modulus, final failure strain, and failure behavior of three kinds of UACS laminates are obtained. It is found that the specimen width significantly affects the tensile testing properties of UACS laminates. The tensile strength, longitudinal modulus, and final failure strain increase with the specimen width increase. The failure behavior is also different for the specimen with different width. Abrupt and large delamination propagation dominate the final failure behavior for specimens with width less than 20 mm and almost no fiber breakage in 0° plies are observed. In contrast, relatively slow and long delamination growth process is observed and a few broken fibers are observed in 0° plies of the fractured specimens with width larger than 20 mm. Therefore, it is worth noting that the effects of specimen width on the tensile testing properties are significant and should be considered in the evaluation of the tensile properties of UACS laminates when the specimen width is less than 25 mm. Specimen with width equal to or larger than 25 mm is recommended to obtain reliable tensile testing results for the UACS laminates.

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